

The Importance of Youth Education in the Development of the New Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The formation of the spiritual and moral foundations of the individual was announced through historical and cultural values, as well as the customs of the people. Therefore, a responsible approach to the education of young people is a necessary necessity for all eras and times. In turn, this required changes in the organization and content of school activities aimed at creating the spiritual and moral foundations of all social institutions and, first of all, society as a whole. The issue of education and upbringing has always been gaining urgent importance and discussed in this paper.

Key points: education, special recognition, young generation, development, national mentality, responsible approach, comprehensive reforms.

It is known from history that the education and maturation of young people is a very complex continuous process. At this point, family, neighborhood, school, public organizations, environment, mass media, art, literature have a direct influence on youth education. Therefore, a responsible approach to the education of young people is a necessary necessity for all eras and times. The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, from the beginning of his presidency, paid attention to the issue and education of the youth. Of course, the President's attention to youth as a strategic task was met with special recognition by experts, scientists and the general public. It is known from worldly development that young people have always been recognized as an active layer of society. In this regard, this regularly forming layer requires constant guidance and support. In the words of our country's president Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "The words of the great Greek scientist Aristotle, who is honored as the "First Teacher" in the East, "The fate of the motherland is decided by the education of the youth", were spoken 350 years ago. Therefore, the issue of education and upbringing has always been gaining urgent importance since the time when humanity began to live a conscious life. Therefore, educating young people who deeply understand the responsibility and conscientiously feel it today is an urgent task of today. It is worth noting that the education of the young generation has become extremely important and relevant in all times. After all, today's demands require serious thinking about youth education. It shows how important it is to study the problems that arise in the field of youth education in a timely manner. At this point, the processes related to youth education, which determine the future of any people and nation, are becoming an urgent issue today. In this regard, it is an urgent task to educate our youth based on the high ethical rules that reflect our national mentality, based on the requirements of today's times.

In ancient times, Aristotle founded a Lyceum and Plato Academy and served to raise the level of education of the population, while our moderns paid special attention to the education of young people by opening schools at their own expense. As it is stated: "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good upbringing, the greatest poverty is ignorance!" giving an example of the wise words, mastering modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true

enlightenment and high culture is becoming a continuous vital need, in order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also members of our society as a whole, first of all, science he emphasized the need for enlightenment, high spirituality, and that in the absence of knowledge, backwardness, ignorance and, of course, cases of straying from the right path are observed. In order to implement comprehensive reforms aimed at "creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance" in our country, there is an increasing need for dedicated and sought-after specialists with modern knowledge and skills in various fields and industries. Accordingly, effective and consistent measures are being implemented by the head of our state in order to meet the long-term need of educated and talented personnel of our society, to provide the economy with competitive specialists. As the President noted about this: "As we have set ourselves the great goal of establishing the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, for this we must create the environment and conditions that will educate the new Khorezms, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Baburs." . In this, first of all, development of education and training, establishment of a healthy lifestyle, promotion of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea. In order to achieve this goal, creating ample opportunities for our young people to set great goals and achieve them, and providing all-round support, should be the top priority for all of us. Only then will our children become a great and powerful force that will fulfill the age-old dreams of our people. Because today, when it comes to the reforms implemented in the field of youth education, it is important to deeply explain the essence of our great history, great scholars and thinkers, national customs, traditions and values, the place and importance of the rich heritage of our ancestors in our lives, and the Motherland in our hearts. On the contrary, we should turn this virtue into the strongest principle that unites our people, our nation. After all, a nation with high pride has high values, morale, and strong will. Any great goal can be achieved with such people.

Relying on these qualities, we have become a nation that does not follow others, but on the contrary, always follows them. We set an example for others with knowledge, enlightenment, and culture. It is known from history that in the development stage of human development, the prestige of a nation is definitely manifested by its spirituality. As a matter of fact, spirituality has a unique miraculous power that makes a person a person. Spirituality is such a powerful force that it is a flag that unites our nation and people towards great and noble goals. Ideological weakness and ideological instability undermine the unity of the nation, the power of the state, and push back its progress." The intensity of today's times emphasizes the importance of spirituality in human life. After all, immorality, indecency, and spiritual poverty drag a person into the vortex of the abyss, and on a large scale, they derail the development of society and create disorder. A person with a conscience and spirituality will definitely love the Motherland. Conscience and spirituality means serving the people and the Motherland from the heart. The fact that such a view is widely and passionately supported by our people, especially by our youth, shows how important spiritual education is.

Therefore, for the honor of the Motherland and the honor of the nation, spirituality is the most effective and powerful weapon in raising a mature and perfect person who understands the goals and interests of the society. In his speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2017, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Today's world youth is the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, as they make up 2 billion people. The future and well-being of our planet depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence. For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests. In this regard, Uzbekistan proposes to develop a generalized international legal document - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth - aimed at the formation and implementation of youth policy in today's conditions of rapid development of globalization and information and communication technologies. Our main goal is to ensure that young people have the opportunity to receive quality education, to create all the necessary conditions for them to realize their abilities and talents" . At the same time, in his speech, the Head of State emphasized that the countries that sign this document must undertake strict obligations to raise this sector to the

level of one of the main and important vital priorities of their social policy. will pass. The intensity of today's times requires serious thinking about the problems arising in the spiritual sphere, the preservation and promotion of the spirituality of our people, especially in the preservation and protection of the hearts and minds of the young generation from the influence of various harmful ideas and ideologies. It is known from worldly development that upbringing and education cannot be separated from each other, these two processes are mutually harmonious, organized on a continuous basis only when they are polite, have moral qualities, high spirituality, at the same time knowledgeable, educates patriotic young people who are smart, mentally and physically healthy, have a broad worldview and thinking, and possess modern professions. Precisely, these factors, the work being carried out on the scientific and technological reform of youth education in Uzbekistan on a modern basis, require its formation on the basis of scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on the needs of today.

In short, the concept presents a new, systematic approach to education, the social-pedagogical possibilities of the family, pre-school education, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher education institutions, neighborhoods in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child. sets the ultimate goal of bringing to the surface and raising the scientific-methodical unity among them to a new level. Further development of the system of spiritual education through the successful implementation of the concept of "continuous spiritual education" is of particular importance. Based on the requirements of the concept of "Continuous spiritual education", systematic work is being carried out to bring the educational work in primary classes to a state that meets today's requirements.

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